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The Impact Of Instructor Type Of Formative Assessment In A Digital Training Environment On The Skills Of Developing Flipped Classroom Technique And Self Efficacy Among The Higher Education Teachers In Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of the instructor type of formative assessment in a digital training environment on developing skills of flipped classroom instructional strategy and self efficacy among the higher education teachers. The research design is a quasi experiment consisted control and experimental groups, the sample comprised thirty higher instructors from Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma who were purposively sampled and divided into two, fifteen each for the control and experimental groups; two instruments were employed to collect data from the sample; (1) Google forms forty five items flipped classroom cognitive and performance skills test (MCQ), (2) Google forms forty five items self efficacy questionnaire (SEQ). The instruments were validated by two experts in educational technology field at Alexandria University Arab republic of Egypt. The General Cronbach Alpha internal consistency of the two instruments were determined as $\alpha = 0.78$ and 0.98 . Johnson equation was used to determine the distinguishing factor for each item of the cognitive and performance test and easiness and difficulty margin of each question of the test. The research outcome elucidated that instructor type of formative assessment implemented in a digital training environment is extremely well positive on improving the cognitive and performance skills of the trainees and their self efficacy and confidence; it's recommended that higher training institutions and other relevant agencies in education sector should consider adopting the flipped classroom approach as one of the instructional strategies and instructor controlled formative assessment as one of the modes of evaluation of students performance especially in courses that require students active participation and immediate feedback.

Keywords: Instructor type, formative assessment, digital training environment, flipped classroom skills, self efficacy

INTRODUCTION

The growing acceptance of digitized training environments has essentially customized instructional approaches in higher education, with flipped classroom instructional approach emerging as a vital technique to improve trainees' engagement, collaboration and the overall learning outcomes. In this discourse, formative assessment which is an ongoing assessment of the trainees training progress has

become essential and effective means of scaffolding both trainees and their instructors towards achieving instructional objectives. However, the effectiveness of formative assessment in a digital training environment, particularly in terms of improving instructors' skills in implementing the flipped classroom model, is still under review.

This research investigates the impact of the instructor type of formative assessment i.e. instructor-led assessment on the development of flipped classroom skills and the self-efficacy of higher education teachers in Katsina State. Self-efficacy means an individual's conviction on his competency to effectively carry through some tasks; its extreme important for trainers to self trust themselves in adopting new approaches to instruction like the flipped classroom instructional strategy. Teachers' appreciation on how formative assessment practices reshape their perceptions on their capacity to use the strategy and provide worthy insights for them to improve their training activities and stimulate more impactful learning in a digital training environment.

Assessment occurs in two forms, formative and summative type. Summative assessment is traditional and product type, it is common and holistic in nature and widely accepted by educational institutions as a means of evaluation. It is design to determine the instructors' instruction quality and students' performance at the end of a unit, term or semester, summative assessment tools include tests, end of semester exams, final project, thesis or Dissertation. (Pereira & Moe, 2014).

While summative assessment is a product assessment, formative assessment focus on the process, hence the name assessment for learning, it is one of the crucial innovations that enjoy a wide acceptance today in many educational institutions of learning, it provide an in process, continuous and diagnostic data related to the students' needs and achievement within a particular domain of learning. Formative assessment is viewed as the frequent, interactive, ongoing classroom assessment conducted to ascertain the present students learning needs and progress, with a view to adapt the instructional strategy to meet the individual learners need and improve their performance and achievement.(Anderson & Palm, 2017)

Formative assessment is design to address some pit falls of summative assessment, the process create an enabling environment for students to demonstrate their understanding and engagement in the learning process, at the same time express their areas of difficulties related to the present lesson, the feedback enable instructors to reconstruct and remold their methods and resources in order to rehabilitate and reshape learners understanding.

Various techniques of formative assessment exists, the common among them include the classroom observations, quizzes inform of multiple choice questions, check boxes, fill in the blank, assignments, class work, class demonstration, exit tickets, online discussion, journals, net folio, students' generated questions and concept maps, the choice of technique to be employed depends on instructors' professionalism and level of the learners.

Formative assessment could be performed by peer (trainee to trainee), self and instructor with a sole purpose to obtain feedback for adjustment of instructional methods to alleviate learning difficulties and maximize achievement

Instructor type assessment is traditionally teacher controlled type, in this type, the instructor is responsible for the delivery of test items and feedback, and he is opportune to express and clarify the instructional objectives in every lesson, and at the same time engage the trainees for a dialogue to determine their experience level related to the topic of discussion, (diagnostic). (Bayissa & Jote, 2019)

Problem of the research:

The favorable reception of progressive training strategies such as flipped classroom instructional method requires instructors to develop some specific abilities and self-confidence; However, in Katsina state, many teachers in the higher institutions of learning find it difficult to put through such type of strategies due to lack of adequate technological training and support.

Digital training environment offer an elastic possibility for professional development, but its effectiveness largely depends on the inclusion of a well structured assessment type like the instructor type of formative assessment technique, this technique enable trainees to obtain an instant personalized learning feedback, differentiated and collaborative learning guidance and stimulates skill development and self confidence.

In spite of all the immense potentiality of these techniques, limited studies have explored the impact of the instructor led assessment on the acquisition of flipped classroom skill and self efficacy especially in a resource constrained schools. Therefore this study aims to examine how the instructor type of formative assessment in a digital environment impacted these factors among higher education teachers in Katsina state.

Objectives of the research

The objectives of the research is to investigate the influence of the instructor type of formative assessment in a digital training environment on developing flipped classroom skills, and self efficacy among higher education teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria. Specifically:-

- 1) To determine the impact of instructor type of formative assessment in a digital training environment on developing flipped classroom cognitive and performance skills among higher education teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria
- 2) To determine the impact of instructor type of formative assessment in a digital training environment on improving self efficacy among higher education teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Research hypothesis

This research was guided by the under listed hypotheses:-

- 1) There is no statistically significant difference at the level ($p \leq 0.05$) between the mean scores of the control and experimental groups in the application of the flipped classroom performance and cognitive skills test in favor of the experimental group.
- 2) There is no statistically significant difference at the level ($p \leq 0.05$) between the mean scores of the control and experimental groups in the application of self efficacy questionnaire in favor of experimental group.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Formative assessment supported the views of constructivism, that learners' learning and thoughts are scaffolded, as they are able to acquire feedback data about standards and criteria of their assessment and usually put into practice to address their needs.(Vandepol, Volman, Ort & Beihuizen, (2015; Abtahi, 2017).

Thus according to this principle learners zone of actual development (ZAD) is determine through formative assessment and then scaffold their learning to reach zone of proximal development, (Social constructivism).

Formative assessment or assessment for learning is coined with radical and collaborative constructivism thought, Dagar & Yandev (2016) that effective learning occurs when learners learn through active process, engagement, collaboration and build upon with prior knowledge. It's trying to describe an informal technique of assembling students learning details so that instructors use that information to determine their achievement on a particular learning target.

Instructor type of formative assessment:

This form of formative type of assessment can be viewed in the constructivists and behaviorists theoretical perspectives. In the constructivists view instructor formative type of assessment emphasize on knowledge acquisition through shared knowledge between the teachers and learners, where teachers acts as coaches, facilitators and share some part of authority with the learners, Mohammed & Kinyo, (2016). Thus emphasis is on learning through practical, experimentations, tasks, projects, enquiry, discovery and analysis.

On behaviorists' perspectives, Mohammed & Kinyo (2016) described it as the type of formative assessments that reflects learning as a cognitive process, individualized and differentiated instruction through tasks, projects, readings, writings and assessments alone with the use of teachers' manuals. This type of assessment is traditional, instructor administered and controlled formative type in which the instructor solely administer the assessment materials to the trainees and provide and utilized the feedback to adjust or modified the instruction to address the difficulties and needs determined through the assessment data.

The instructor type formative assessment corresponds to the principles of Vygotsky's scaffolding theory, which addresses the learning needs of different categories of learners as groups and as

individuals, with aid of specific diagnosis procedures aimed at determining current learners' performance so as to project their future performance after intervention, zone of actual to proximal developments ZAD to ZPD.

According to Shabani, Khatib & Ebadi (2010), Bayissa & Jote (2019) the role of the instructor in formative assessment practices are not limited to diagnose and address the individual and groups of learners immediate needs, adapt the instructional resources and instruction according to the needs and peculiarities of the learners, offer individualized and differential learning opportunity to ensure progress of the learners, ensure the provision of formative feedback and determine learners learning progress, stimulate the learners so as to improve their commitment to learning and to assist the learners to identify their strength and weakness as well as their immediate needs.

Digital training environment:

Digital training is a sub set of e-training. Thus e-training is a general term representing all electronic and other forms of internet base and technology mediated training, it is viewed as a form of training influenced by portable small electronic gadgets; the portability and smaller size of mobile devices made it very popular in today's e-training system.

Digital training has been connected to connectivism theoretical views; the idea is that learning and learning activities surpass only physical environment, rather occurs both in a physical and virtual spaces and negates time constraints so as to enable learners access to contents synchronous and asynchronous any time anywhere.

In the connectivists' idea, Herlo & Vlairo, (2016) acknowledged that remembering and understanding are unique opinions, and that can be accessed from diverse environments independent of human minds connected from various nodes of information. Thus the theory tries to established relationship between knowledge transmission and acquisition and the digital age as well as how digital technology devices such as computers, mobile devices, (mobile phones, android phones), web browsers, wikis, Google chrome, and social network provide a new paradigm environment for teaching and learning.

Digital training on the constructivists and connectivists views Herlo & Vlairo (2016), Bhattacharjee (2015) can be summarized below:

- Learning and knowledge in mobile training environment rest in the diversity of opinions (Diverse nodes for learning sources)
- Learning and contents in a digital training environment should be flexible (Learning flexibilities)
- Learning shift from teacher to students control (mobility of learning environment and contents)
- Learning is a process of connectivity (Knowledge from divers sources, digital repositories)
- Learning should be autonomous (independent learning)

To buttress the above, Oyediran (2021) described digital training devices as technology devices that serve other purposes by conducting other educational activities such as surveys, audio and video clips recording, picture and image shoot and view, and could enable the user to share and receive data from educational elites. This type of training environment is used to deliver instruction in a different instructional strategies; one of these strategies is flipped classroom.

The Flipped classroom

Flip classroom has been rooted from different instructional theories cut across the three theoretical schools of thoughts, Behaviorism, Cognitivism and Constructivism.

Notably in a flipped classroom learning, learners are exposed to training materials online in video and audio clips, power point, blogs and word documents usually online when they are at home and work and process them through watching the video, listening to podcasts, reading and doing activities related to remembering and understanding before application and analysis inform of home work and assignments as class activities. In accordance with the principles of behaviorists approach to learning stipulates that learning or behavior changes occur when the learners are reinforce and given the enabling environment. Instructors are responsible for the preparation and provision of the materials to the learners via a stipulated web link, where learners privately accessed.

According to Broady (2016) flipped classroom learning is has been viewed as a form of hybrid learning that connect face to face and online meeting at different time which gives learners opportunities to work both at home and in school with intervention of mobile devices, these activities corresponds to the principles of social constructivism and connectivism approach to instruction, that is learning through engagement, activities and via digital technology in a diverse environment to enhance and facilitate transmission and delivery,

To flip a classroom is far beyond bonding the online off campus activities and on campus classroom activities, there are some vital issues that instructors willing to flip must consider before flipping their learners, these include flipping the mind, time management issue, technology issue, training of the trainers, trainees and parents about flip model, (Hojeij & Ayber, 2017).

The qualitative and quantitative studies to examine the repercussions of formative assessment on the academic behavior, success and anxiety of students, Kincal & Ozan (2018), Galle & Kukwi (2020), Huism (2018), Musa & Islam (2020), Kondri (2020), elucidated that when it’s applied as a means to enhance the variables there were positive results from both students and the instructors.

An investigation carried out by Sanaifer & Nafari (2018), Zhang (2018), Ikpi, Ojating & Mpantor (2019), revealed that formative assessment differentiated significantly on the participants increased motivation without any gender dichotomy, this indicated that formative assessment is effective on both male and female learners if administered and given the same treatment.

The work of Tigelaar & Sins (2020) revealed that teachers participated in the instructor assessment scored higher than those in peer and self assessment, also high degree of collegiality stimulates and improve teacher adaptation.

Experimental design:

This research is a quasi design adopted by the researchers to determine the effect of treatment to the sample of the experimental group. This form of research design enables the researchers to compare outcomes of a group between control and experimental on skills in developing flipped classroom strategy and self efficacy.

Table 1: Experimental design

Research Sample	Treatments	Assessment
<p>Experimental group</p> <p>The instructor type of formative assessment</p>	<p>Flipped classroom cognitive and performance skills development treatment course materials (FCCPSDTCM), in a digital training environment. instructor type of formative assessment & feedback,</p>	<p>Flipped classroom skills cognitive and performance test.</p>
<p>Control group</p> <p>Traditional assessment</p>	<p>Flipped classroom cognitive and performance skills development treatment course materials (FCCPSDTCM), in a digital training environment. Traditional assessment</p>	<p>Self efficacy questionnaire.</p>

From the table 1 above, it can be confirmed that the research contained an experimental and control group; these groups comprised higher education teachers who studied Flipped classroom strategy development skills treatment course materials in a digital training environment using the instructor type of formative assessment and those that studied same using traditional assessment technique.

Area of the study

The research is restricted to the following:

- a) Area of the study: Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma Katsina State Nigeria
- b) Topic: Design, development and implementation of flipped classroom skills in a digital training environment.

Research subjects

- a) The research sample was purposively selected from the academic staff of Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma Katsina State.
- b) Period of treatment: The exercise took place in the summer semester of 2023/2024 academic session.

Research instruments

The researchers prepared two instruments to elicit data from the research subjects. These instruments are:-

1. Flipped classroom cognitive and performance skills test (FCCPST; MCQ)
2. Self efficacy questionnaire (SEQ)

Validity and reliability of the research instruments

After preparation of the research instruments which include the design of the two instruments, composing their items, sequencing of the composed items for each instrument, the two instruments were subjected to various tests including the test of validity, reliability, easiness and difficulty margin for each item of the cognitive test, the distinguishing factors for each question of the cognitive test and the timing of the cognitive test, in order to ascertain the consistency and acceptability of the instruments to accurately measure the traits they are designed to assess.

For the validity of the two instruments, the researchers sent the flipped classroom cognitive and performance skills test and the self efficacy questionnaire to two professors in educational technology field at Alexandria University Arab republic of Egypt, all their observations in the area of construct, content and face were strictly considered.

To test the reliability of the research instruments, the researchers conducted a one week pilot study with fifteen members of the research population, after which the two instruments were applied in Google forms via Google classroom, responses were collected and Cronbach alpha (α) coefficient was calculated using Spss software version 23 and the internal consistency of the items of the cognitive and performance skills test was ($\alpha = 0.78$) representing 78% consistency while ($\alpha = 0.98$) representing 98% consistency were realized for the self efficacy questionnaire. It was finally ruled that the two instruments were valid and reliable for data collection.

Moreover, the researchers adopted item difficulty index (p-value) to determine the easiness and difficulty margin of the items of the cognitive and performance skills test, the computed results showed that the margin ranges from 0.5 and 0.85, out of the forty five questions forty questions were ranged as accepted and good in terms of easiness and difficulty while five questions were low and were adjusted prior to the compilation of the final form of the test.

For the distinguishing factor for each question of the cognitive and performance skills test, the researchers used Johnson equation to calculate distinguishing factor, the question which the distinguishing factor is less than 0.2 is regarded as an undistinguished question; the results obtained were ($p = 0.222$) for all the questions which indicated that all the test questions were distinguishable. (Fu'ad, Al-Bahiy, Al-sayyed, 2011)

The timing of the test

To determine time for the test questions, the researchers used the procedure below: The researchers recorded the time for start and completion by the 15 pilot study sample and the distribution is given below

25,30,35,30,40,45,45,50,30,35,40,40,50,55,60

Total time = $610/15 = 40.7$

Therefore the total test time allotted was 40 minutes

Google classroom

The researchers adopted Google classroom as the digital training environment, the rationale for the choice is that the environment have satisfied some certain criteria for the selection of a digital learning environment for a capacity building training programs which include cost effectiveness (it's a free

tool in Google store), user friendliness and easy accessibility, its flexible and compatible to a diversified training contents, it supports synchronous and asynchronous interaction, it facilitate formative assessments and feedback, it handle higher volume of users at a time, it integrate with other Google tools like Microsoft office, Google work spaces and other eLearning tools, it enable instructors to track the progress of their trainees and can easily grade their work via a paperless format.

The trainers created a Google classroom (instructor type classroom) specifically for the training program, and access code was assigned to the participants to join as students. Moreover, the procedures for creating and joining a Google classroom have been posted (inform of text and video) to them via a dedicated whatsapp forum. The trainers uploaded and share all the training resources inform of videos, text, power points, podcast, pdf documents and links in the classroom in units, interaction and collaborative activities took place in the chat wall of the Google classroom.

Implementation of the basic experiment study

The basic experiment has been implemented within two weeks, from 15th – 30th September 2024, the training covers four units of flipped classroom development skills on pre-class, in-class and post-class activities; (concept exploration, demonstration and application and meaning making) below is the time table for the basic experimental study.

Table 2: Time table for the implementation of basic experiment: two weeks, begins from 15th – 30th October, 2024

Weeks	Treatment/ activity	Assessment
Week one 15 th – 22 nd September, 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General guidelines and objectives of the training 1. Introduction of the first module: Flipped classroom concept exploration (pre-class activities: watching videos, listening to podcasts, readings articles). - Activities. In-class: (hands-on-activities, quizzes, presentations, discoveries, summaries) 2. The second module: Demonstration and application, pre-class; (watching video about developing active in-class learning activities through application, analysis, group discussion, problem solving exercises, peer tutoring, etc.) - Activities. In-class: (Hands-on- activities such as demonstration, projects, discoveries, personalized learning, peer instruction etc.) 	<p>Post-class: (meaning making) Through reflective podcast in form of online quizzes, online discussion, formative assessment and feedback</p>
Week two 23 rd – 30 th September ,2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The third module: Pre-class :Technology training(videos about screen capture technology e.g. screen cast-o-matic, screen flow, navigation of resources through Google, slideshare, vimeo for videos, scribd for pdf docs, learning management systems in a video and power point presentation etc) - Activities: In-class (hands-on- training on how to create video content, podcast, interactive power point, pdf articles, how to create Google classroom) 2. Classroom management: Pre-class: (video on flipped classroom sitting arrangements, flipped classroom group activities, group discussions, personalized learning) - Activities. In-class: (practicing how to manage flipped classroom activities, supporting trainees class activities, monitoring the active learning processes) 	<p>Post-class: (meaning making) through reflective podcast inform of online quizzes, online discussion, formative assessment and feedback.</p>

The researchers used ADDIE instructional design model which consists five basic stages (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) to prepare the used treatments materials and the implementation of the research treatments.

Application of research instruments

Upon completion of the two weeks basic training including the theory and practical phases related to the flipped classroom development skills, the researchers applied the two research instruments online via the digital training environment in order to collect data and be able to make statistical analysis to determine the effectiveness of the training exercise in the areas of cognitive and performance skills as well as the self efficiency of the higher education teachers. Detailed of the analysis is given below:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the collation of pre-test and post-test data, the researchers used descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation, paired sample t-test (X, SD & t-test at 0.05 level of significance) for analysis to determine the impending significant difference in the cognitive and performance skills and self efficiency of the experimental group and the result is presented below:

1) There is no statistically significant difference at the level ($p \leq 0.05$) between the mean scores of the control and experimental groups in the application of the flipped classroom performance and cognitive skills test in favor of the experimental group.

Table 2: Mean scores, standard deviation and paired sample t – test scores concerning control and experimental groups on cognitive and performance skills test:

Experimental group	Test type	No	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean difference	t-value	2 tailed sig. P value	Remark	η^2
Instructor type	Control group	30	18.1667	9.878	8.66	2.689	0.012	Sig	0.19 large effect
	Experimental group	30	26.8333	14.36					

Result from table 2 above exposed the magnificent of instructor formative assessment type on cognitive and performance skills success of the research sample in flipped classroom development skills. The results obtained indicated an increase of the average scores of 8.66 between control and experimental groups on application of the test materials in favor of experimental group, having average scores of 26.8333 (SD, 14.36) against 18.1667 (SD, 9.878) for the control group.

The computed p values were 0.012 below the 0.05 confidence level. Since the p value of 0.012 is less than the 0.05 threshold, the hypotheses has been accepted, meaning that instructor type of formative assessment is splendid on improving the cognitive and performance skills of the experimental group on flipped classroom development skills. The effect size value $\eta^2 = 0.19$ revealed a very high effect size between control and experimental group, which further revealed the impressiveness of instructor led formative type of assessment on improving cognitive and performance skills of flipped classroom development for the higher education teachers.

In the light of constructivism thought, experiential and situated approach, viewed that trainees' epistemological path lies on his ability to share and work for knowledge creation through the use of instructors guide and facilitation, as well as divisive responsibilities and the application of prior experience to build a novel comprehension. Thus trainees learn effectively by construction knowledge in their minds through the influence of interaction with their instructors, which has been part of the objectives and effectiveness of the instructor type of formative assessment. (Dagar & Yandev, 2016; Mohammed & Kinyo 2020)

Supporting this result further, Bayissa and Jote (2019) revealed that instructor assessment stimulates trainees to improve their commitment and understanding and that to ensure learning progress, to elaborate further, Karim (2015) opined that formative assessment enhances trainee's positive feelings towards learning.

2) There is no statistically significant difference at the level ($p \leq 0.05$) between the mean scores of the control and experimental groups in the application of self efficacy questionnaire in favor of experimental group.

Table 3: Mean, standard deviation and t – test in respect of the control and experimental group on the application of self efficacy questionnaire

Experimental group	No	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean difference	t-value	2 tailed sig p-value	Remark
Control group	30	34.833	8.95230	3.500	1.585	0.118	Not Sign.
Experimental group	30	38.333	8.12970				

Table 3 above, vindicated that there were no wide statistical margin between the average scores of the two groups on the self confidence of higher education teachers related to the instructor type of formative assessment and digital training environment. The computed α t – value 1.585 is higher than the α 0.05 significance level which can be interpreted as statistically insignificant, since the 2 tailed t value 1.585 is greater than α 0.05 confidence level, therefore hypotheses is rejected, which implied that instructor type of formative assessment is moderately effective on self efficacy of the training sample.

Based on Albert Bandura’s self efficacy theory posits that instructors with high self efficacy are more likely to engage students, apply more effective instructional strategies and persist via challenges. Moreover, the Social constructivists’ theory emphasized that observational learning which part of instructor type of formative assessment develops teachers’ motivation and self efficacy. (Bhati & Sethy, 2022).

Supporting the result, Lev Vygotsky’s constructivism idea stressed that collaborative training environments through formative assessments monitored by instructors improves trainees self efficacy, stimulates peer scaffolding and shared understanding which further improve educational outcomes. (Artino, 2020)

To complement more on the above, instructor type of formative assessment has been credited to offering individualized and differentiated training opportunities, ensures trainees improved cognitive, performance achievements and molded their level of confidence and competence towards learning. The instructors in this type of assessment can instantly adapt the instructional strategies and resources to address the immediate needs of the trainees. (Bayissa & Jote, 2019).

Furthermore, from the researcher’s experience in the application of the experiment, though digital training is not a familiar approach in Nigerian system of education which may hardly be fully implemented in the near future due to peculiarities, the experimental sample exhibited a positive to some extent to complete activities, meet the instructor for clarifications, comment in the group’s forum, this was because instructor type activities resembled with the familiar traditional approach of instruction in our educational institutions, teachers are used to stand and deliver instruction, where teachers absorbed and reduced anxiety and stress, the experimental group feels as if it was the traditional approach and feels some kind of comfort, confidence and relaxation during the training.

Another important point from the researcher’s experience in the application of the experiment is that the trainees had an opportunity to receive direct guidance from the instructor, this alleviate their phobia for learning with technology or in a digital training environment, the fact that all activities were supervised and managed by the instructor has boosted their confidence and positively impacted their self efficacy.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research results indicated that instructor type of formative assessment implemented in flipped classroom development skills led to an extremely well positive improvement on the cognitive and performance skills of the trainees as well as their self efficacy and confidence. The apocalypse further highlights the relevance of the instructor type of formative assessment and its potentiality on enhancing the effectiveness of various instructional pedagogies like flipped classroom, which enhances learners’ engagement, comprehension, motivation and confidence.

In view of the results and conclusion; it's recommended that higher training institutions and other relevant agencies in education sector should consider the integration of flipped classroom as one of the instructional strategies and instructor type of formative assessment as the mode of evaluation of students performance especially in courses that require students active participation and immediate feedback. Higher institutions of learning should also boost the morale of their teachers by investing fully in technological infrastructure so as to enable them have access to digital devices and internet connectivity to facilitate the implementation of formative assessments and flipped instruction in a digital training environment.

More professional development training should be organized for teachers with adequate training facilities and a little incentive to equip them with the latest skills for the design and implementation of the digital training at anytime and anywhere.

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